

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURE 3

Supplemental Figure 3. Time course of recovery of OAT1-mediated [³H]PAH uptake by CHO-OAT1 cells after pre-treatment with telmisartan. The cells were pre-treated for 30 min with telmisartan (0.5 μ M) or no telmisartan (control). Following telmisartan exposure, the cells were rinsed and incubated in Waymouth buffer containing 10% fetal bovine serum for the time points indicated (recovery time after telmisartan washout) prior to measuring the uptake of [³H]PAH for 15 sec.